

Sheath rot (ShR) severity due to rice bug infection

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A high infestation of rice bugs *Leptocoris acuta* (Thunb.) (15-20/panicle) was observed at ACRI Sep-Oct 1990. ShR [causal organism:

Sarocladium oryzae (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw.] incidence was also high.

We conducted a greenhouse study to examine the role of rice bugs in ShR infection. IR20 seeds were sown in 20- × 40-cm peat trays. Four weeks after germination, 2 seedlings/pot were transplanted to 10-cm earthen pots filled with wetland soil. The plants were kept in insect-proof cages in the greenhouse.

Laboratory-reared rice bug masses were collected and released on the plants at booting at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 bugs/tiller, with a no-bug control. After 48 h of feeding, the plants were sprayed to runoff with a spore suspen-

sion of 5×10^7 conidia/ml, and placed immediately in a 100% relative humidity chamber maintained at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Inoculated plants were then transferred to greenhouse benches.

Each treatment had about 20 tillers with five replications. Individual tillers were evaluated daily for ShR infection using a 0-9 scale (0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% sheath area affected, 3 = 1-5%;

5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, and 9 = more than 50% sheath area affected).

Bug-infested plants exhibited typical ShR symptoms within 12 d after spraying with spore suspension. Disease incidence was low on noninfested plants. ShR severity and percent of infected tillers were related to bug population (Fig. 1, 2). □

Farm machinery

A simple closed chemical transfer attachment for knapsack sprayers

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Operators of small sprayers are exposed to pesticides at all stages of use, but especially while measuring and mixing concentrated formulations. The risk of contamination can be minimized by using an alternative system to transfer chemicals from the original container to the sprayer tank.

We developed and tested a simple closed system for transfer of liquid chemicals to knapsack sprayers. It consists of a 1-liter plastic container

fitted with a manually operated piston pump. The pump barrel is transparent and graduated, allowing up to 35 ml pesticide/stroke to be withdrawn from the bottle (see figure). The outlet of the pump is connected to the tank through a nondrip connector that permits flow only when connection is made. The system is mounted to the sprayer tank with a clamp.

We compared operator exposure with this system with two conventional handling methods: mixing a measured quantity of chemical with water in a bucket and then pouring the solution into the tank, and pouring the chemical directly into the sprayer tank. The experiments were laid out in randomized complete block design with five replica-

1. Effect of rice bug population on ShR severity.

Effect of rice bug population on percentage of selected tillers.

Closed chemical transfer system for knapsack sprayer and system attached to a knapsack sprayer.